

Supplementary information

A European platform trial for major depressive disorder

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Drug screening and collaborative prioritization

Candidate drugs to launch the pharmacological domain (oral) were sourced from two systematic reviews (Scott et al. *J Psychopharmacol* 2023;37:268-278 and Fabri et al. *Prog Neuropsychopharmacol Biol Psychiatry* 2021;104:110050) plus suggestions received from the scientific community during the public consultation. This led to a list of 59 candidate drugs. Of these, 15 were excluded because they were either not available in oral form, not commercially available, or not licensed for human use in EU/UK. For the resulting long list of 44 drugs, the Berlin team systematically screened and summarized the available evidence from animal models and clinical studies. In the next steps, each national lead was requested to nominate up to two drugs for short listing, resulting in a final list of six candidates: Agomelatine, aripiprazole, pentoxifylline, pramipexole, semaglutide (oral), and trazodone. For these, we conducted an updated evidence synthesis (systematic searches in Pubmed and clinicaltrials.gov). The national leads then allocated 12 points to their drug(s) of choice for a preliminary ranking of the shortlist. The results (see below) were presented and discussed by the Trial Management Group (TMG) on December 17, 2025. The lived experience team and representatives of the project's funder were provided with the ranking as well as the synthesized evidence for each medicine, and had a veto right for any number of shortlisted and ranked drugs.

Based on the voting results and the ranked short list of six drugs, trazodone and pramipexole have been identified as the top candidates. These will therefore be the first two drugs to launch the pharmacological domain. Pramipexole will be used in its extended-release formulation to improve tolerability. The voting results and the discussion clearly showed a strong interest in the third ranked drug, oral semaglutide. The recommendation from the group was therefore that oral semaglutide will be lined up to potentially replace either of the two starting drugs in case they meet criteria for early termination at interim analysis. The overall prioritization and design recommendation was reviewed and approved by the Lived Experience team as well as the Wellcome Trust.

Supplementary Figure 1: Network map of EU-PEARLDIVER

Supplementary Figure 2: EU-PEARLDIVER design

Supplementary Figure 3: EU-PEARLDIVER governance structure

Supplementary Figure 4: Initial domain of the EU-PEARLDIVER platform trial